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Is Women Empowerment– A Far Fetched Reality

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Abstract

Women play a great role in all walks of life of an individual. There is a saying that ‘The hand that rocks the cradle rules the world. Today we find women making a great contribution in all fields. We find women as great scientists, doctors, lawyers, teachers, pilot etc. In families’ women as daughters, wife, mother, sister etc play a great role owing to their selfless services. Yet we find discrimination of women owing to gender in larger perspective. This cannot be ignored as it affects their progress. They are subjected to ill-treatment in their job roles and in the family. Domestic violence is still the order of the day. We cannot ignore the fact that the scenario is changing. But still we find the instances of women harassment and stereotyping in Medias and tele serials. Wage disparity is the order of the day especially in low profile jobs and fashion industry. Still we have a big list of women in lead in various sectors. Women empowerment will become a reality if the people at home and society will acknowledge their contribution.

Key Words: Empowerment, Reality, Fetched

1.0 Introduction:

Women play a great role in all walks of life. There is a saying “Behind every successful man, there is a women”. Today we find women excelling in various fields. The role of women as daughters, wife, daughter-in-laws, grandmother etc in families and their professional roles are really non-definable. Generally women are multitasking and known for their multi skill activities. Studies show that on daily average, women work 1 hour more than men. But still the perception of women is generally stereotyped and idealised in negative way. This article is to highlight the point, and raise the question

1. Is women empowerment far from Reality?
2. To Analyse the Factors for discrimination,
3. To study the areas where women are major contributors,
4. To analyse the political participation of women

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5. To analyse the contribution of notable women in various areas
6. To identify possible solutions for gender improvement

1.1 Is women empowerment far from Reality?

Gender division is a form of built hierarchy, where the difference is not only based on biology, but also on social expectations and stereotypes. We are very well aware of the social belief that boys and girls are brought up to believe that the main responsibility of women is house work and child rearing. Our society is still a patriarchal society where the entire family is under the father. In fact the word ‘patriarchy’ literally means ‘rule by father’. This concept is used to refer to a system that values men more and gives them power over women.

Women generally do all work at home like cooking, cleaning, washing, tailoring looking after children etc. Once a protagonist said. “Man has no children, only a woman has”. To that extent the entire process of domestic chore still lie on the shoulder of women. Women work outside their home too. These days we find woman go to jobs to run the family smoothly and to support the family. In villages women fetch water, collect fuel and work in fields. In urban areas, poor women work as domestic help in middle class homes, while women from middle class work in offices. This leads to a situation of ‘Double burden’ with respect to women. In fact most women do some paid work in addition to domestic work. But usually we find that their work is not valued or paid, if they are only home makers.

Review of Related Literature:

1. Referring to the well-known United Nations quote from 1980 which is still relevant: “Women constitute half the world’s population, perform nearly two-thirds of its work hours, receive one-tenth of the world’s income, and own less than one-hundredth of the world’s property” which is an economic indicator of women status and should be an indicator for the solution of the economic development. This half of the population need to be empowered in order to make change in the economic development.
2. According to Kapur (2001) “Women ‘s empowerment could be considered as a process in which women gain greater share of control over resource material, human and intellectual, like knowledge, ideas and financial resources like money and control over decision making at home, in society and in the nation and to gain power .
3. This has become a reality in many cases, as we see instances were more women than men are enrolled in academic institutions and women pursuing careers in previously male-dominated fields (Miller, 1986).
4. Many laws enacting women’s rights, like the Dowry Prohibition Act 1961, were enacted after India became independent. Act on Preventing, Prohibiting, and Redressing Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplaces (2013) protects women at all workplaces, both organized and unorganized, irrespective of whether they are public or private.

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5. Furthermore, the Indian Constitution prioritizes gender equality, empowering the state to implement positive discrimination measures favouring women. The positive discrimination scope of Article 15 is one example of such a provision. Equal opportunities in the workplace are provided by Article 16.

1.2. Factors for Discrimination:

It is said in Vedic days and during the arrival of Aryans, women had a great esteem and Respect in the society. During the medieval times in India, many restrictions have been followed for women. They were not allowed to pursue their basic education or take up main role in decision making. If women belonged to elite societies, liberal fathers educated their daughters at home. We find instances of women you studied in private without the knowledge of family members. Example madam Rokeya Shekawat and many more. It was a superstitious belief that if women were educated they will soon become a widow. But still we find exemplary contribution of Tara Bai Shinde, who wrote a book called 'Stri Purush Thulna' comparing men and women of the then society. Even Mahatma Gandhi discouraged women participating in Freedom Struggle and stated that women have responsibility towards their family and they are expected to attend to it. But many women like Kasturibai Gandhi and Sarojini Naidu took active participation in mass struggle like Non-Co-operation and civil disobedience movement.

Even in the present century we find the following discrimination:

1. The literacy among women as per 2022 is 70.7% whereas men's literacy rate is 84.7% in higher education also girls enrolment rate is comparatively less. But when it comes for performance in class X and class XII results, we find girls outwit boys.
2. The proportion of women in highly paid and valued job is less.
3. On an average Indian woman works one hour than an average man daily. Yet much of her work is not paid and therefore not valued
4. Though Equal wages Act state that equal wage should be paid for equal work. But the reality is totally different. Starting from cinema to fashion, farm to factories, women are paid less than man. This wage parity exists even in some IT industries
5. Even today in many parts of India parents prefer to have boys and sex selective abortion is still found. In many areas we find 'honour killings, especially if girls find her life partner from other communities.
6. Violence against women is found in many Indian households, especially that of poor
7. Sexual abuse in work places and violent incident in public places if always heard of or read in newspapers or viewed in medias

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8. In television serials women are focused in cruel and arrogant especially as mother-in-law or sister-in-law, though we find rare incidents in real life situations.

1.3 The areas where women are major contributors:

Mostly we find women as teachers, nursing jobs banks, and all formal sectors. They contribute greatly even in their place of work. Today we find women taking up challenging jobs such as loco pilot, auto drivers, pilots and defence. Even in IT industries women occupy around 45% of workforce. Recently we would have heard women could take NDA exams also. So here we could conclude saying that the jobs which were considered to be in the domain of men have seen women equally talented and contributing.

1.4 Role of women in Political life:

In India women's proportion in political life is not very much satisfying. The proportion of women in Legislature is very low. The percentage of elected women in Lok Sabha is around 14.4% of its total strength. Their share in state legislative assemblies is somewhere around 9%. In political representation of women our country stands among the bottom group of Nations. It is a sorry state of affair that India is behind the averages for several developing countries of Africa and Latin America. Even if women become the Chief Minister or even Prime Minister, both the state legislative assemblies and Cabinet is dominated by male members. One way to solve this problem is to make things legally binding to have a fair proportion of women in the elected bodies. Panchayati Raj has successfully done it in India. One third of seats in Local bodies are exclusively reserved for women. That why we find a substantial proportion of women representation in Municipalities and panchayats .i.e 45%

1.5 Economic Empowerment of women:

The term economic empowerment include women's ability to participate equally in economic markets', their access to and control over productive resources, access to decent work, control over their own time, increased voice and agency to represent and meaningful participation in economic decision making at all levels from the households to the international level. Gender difference in the world of work has affected both developed and developing nations. Economies still have laws from preventing women from working in specific jobs. Women migrant workers are the worst sufferers. They are moistly employed in retail, elementary occupations, craft and related trade and clerks.

1.6 contributions of notable women in India as per 2022

The BW business world most influential women 2022 initiative is specifically to celebrate the leaders who are breaking the barriers and creating an impact not only on their companies and organisations but going beyond on the wider scale. The list this year projects 75 leaders. Here we could see top 10 leaders.

1	Falguni Nayar	CEO, Nykaa
2	Hima Kohli	Judge, Supreme Court Of India
3.	Hina Nagarajan	MD & CEO , Diageo, India
4.	Kiran Mazumdar Shaw	Chairperson & Managin Director, Bicon & Bicon , Biologics
5	Nirmala Sitharaman	Finance Minister
6.	Soma Mondal	Chairperson, SAIL
7.	Soumya Swaminathan	Chief Scientist, World Health Organisation
8.	Suchitra Ella	Co-Founder & Joint MD, Bharat Biotech, International
9.	Suneeta Reddy	MD, Apollo hospitals
10	Swati Piramal	Vice Chairperson, Piramal Group

The List is really astonishing. We find considerable number of women those who have left and continuing their efforts in an exemplary manner.

1.7. Possible solution for women empowerment:

There are few solutions listed here for women empowerment:

1. **Boosting self-esteem:** empowered women should go on to empower others.
2. **Shut down negativity:**

Women should shut down negativity as they are often held to unrealistic standards displayed in magazines, on T.V and more recently on social media. Lift women up by taking a stance against negative comments online, at the office, in school and wherever they go.

3. **Be open and honest:**

Without women like Rosa Parks, Malala Yousafzai, and Susan B. Anthony, women wouldn't have the rights we have today. So be open minded and honest to share your problem and bitter experience, harassment you face. This will atleast help other women to be cautious.

4. **Advocate for female colleagues:**

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Be an advocate for your female colleagues. If you find your female colleague experiencing some kind of illtreatment in workplace or anywhere , volunteer to express it to others. Women must work together to empower one- another in work places.

5. Lead by example:

Young women are deeply influenced by their role models. So make sure you are a good role model.

6. Become a Mentor

Become a mentor for young girls and lead them. Seminars and group discussions could be conducted periodically

7. Fight against injustice:

Stand up for women’s right and be a part of the process. Invite the inspiring men and women who could volunteer for this cause and conduct rallies and campaigns. Through this you can help young women to fight against injustice.

1.8 Conclusion:

Empowering women starts from every individual. We should constantly support women around us, by reminding them of their strength. Self awareness and knowing basic laws and enactments from time to time is imperative. If any harassment is encountered, women should develop courage to express it openly to women’s forum and fight for justice as a team. So seeing all these changes and contribution by notable women in various fields women empowerment will be surely a reality

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